

1 **Receptors that identify the TE in the human embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here a collection of
9 receptors that identify the trophectoderm in the embryo during human development.

10 Citations

- 11 1. Alarcon, V.B. and Marikawa, Y., 2022. Trophectoderm formation: regulation of morphogenesis and
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